

BENZIMIDAZOLE AS A REAGENT FOR SILVER *

BY R. L. DUTTA

Benzimidazole has been found to precipitate silver quantitatively in ammoniacal medium. In presence of ammoniacal ethylenediamine tetra-acetate, benzimidazole precipitates only silver, whereas copper, nickel, cobalt, iron, manganese, chromium, cadmium, zinc, mercury, magnesium, etc. remain in solution. Beryllium, titanium, aluminium, uranyl, thorium etc. have been masked by tartrate ion. But in presence of ammonium salts, precipitation is incomplete. In the absence of ammonium salts therefore benzimidazole serves as a specific reagent for silver. The silver benzimidazole precipitate is stable towards heat and light, and a single determination takes much less time as compared to the classical chloride method.

Benzimidazole (I) $C_7H_6N_2$ has long been shown by Feigl and Gleich (*Monatsh.*, 1928, 49, 385) to furnish well-defined salts with copper, cobalt, zinc, cadmium and mercury. The reaction between cobalt and benzimidazole has been used as a test for cobalt (Yagoda, *Microchem.*, 1938, 24, 117). Ghosh (this *Journal*, 1951, 28, 710) has described the preparation of some more copper and nickel complexes and made their magnetic measurements. Recently, Ghosh and Ghosh (*Proc. Ind. Sci. Congress*, 1955, Part III, p. 79) have reported gravimetric estimation of cobalt with this reagent at pH 10. Although rather similar benzotriazole and its 5-bromo derivative have been used by various workers (Remington and Moyer, Dissertation, Abst. No. 24, Ohio State Univ. Press, 1937; Tarasevich, *Vestnik Moskow Univ.*, 1948, 3, No. 10, 161; Cheng, *Anal. Chem.*, 1954, 26, 1038) as a reagent for gravimetric estimation of silver, so far no work with benzimidazole as a reagent for the same element has been reported.

It has now been found that benzimidazole furnishes with silver in ammoniacal medium a white quantitative precipitate (II), which is very stable towards light and heat.

In presence of ammonia, the precipitate coagulates very rapidly and offers no difficulty in filtration. The precipitate is insoluble in hot water, dilute ammonia and benzene, but soluble in acids, pyridine, sodium thiosulphate and potassium cyanide. The composition of the precipitate, when dried at 120° , is $\text{AgC}_7\text{H}_5\text{N}_2$, so that the gravimetric factor for silver becomes 0.4797.

* After this paper was communicated, Ghosh and Ghosh (*Proc. Ind. Sci. Congress*, 1956, Part III, p. 58) have reported the use of benzimidazole for gravimetric estimation of silver in presence of thallium. But di-sodium salt of EDTA or sodium potassium tartrate has not been used for masking other interfering ions.

In presence of ammonia, besides copper, nickel, cobalt, zinc, mercury and cadmium, which give characteristic precipitates with benzimidazole, many other metals, hydroxides of which are insoluble in ammonia, interfere. However, it has been found that if ammoniacal ethylenediamine tetra-acetate (EDTA) is present, benzimidazole precipitates only silver, whereas many other metals are held in solution. Thus Cu, Ni, Co, Mn, Fe, Cr, Mg, Tl^+ , Hg^{II} , Pb, Zn, Cd, etc. have been rendered harmless. Hydroxides of metals like titanium, beryllium are insoluble in EDTA; so they have been masked by tartrate ion. Aluminium, thorium, uranyl also have been masked by tartrate ion. Hg^I will not interfere when oxidised to Hg^{II} state. Similarly, Fe^{II} must be oxidised to the Fe^{III} state because Fe^{II} -EDTA reduces Ag^+ to the metallic state (Pribil *et al.*, *Chem. Listy*, 1953, 47, 88). But the most objectionable interference has been presented by ammonium salts. In presence of ammonium salts, precipitation of silver benzimidazole is incomplete, and consequently the values are low. It may be pointed out here that none of the workers on benzotriazole (*loc. cit.*) has studied the influence of ammonium salts. The present author intends to investigate this point in near future. Of the anions, nitrate, sulphate, acetate, chloride, phosphate, tungstate, vanadate, oxalate, chromate, etc. do not interfere. Thus, in the absence of appreciable quantity of ammonium salts, benzimidazole has been found to be a specific reagent for silver.

EXPERIMENTAL

o-Phenylenediamine (13.5 g.) was heated with 85% formic acid (8.5 c.c.) on a water-bath for about 2 hours. The mixture after cooling was treated with 10% NaOH till distinctly alkaline. The separated benzimidazole was filtered off and finally recrystallised from hot water (yield 10 g.), m. p. 169° (lit. m.p. 170°).

As the reagent was poorly soluble in cold water, a hot 1% aqueous solution was used as the precipitant.

Ammoniacal EDTA solution: Disodium salt of EDTA (7.5-11 g.) was dissolved in 100 c.c. solution containing 20 c.c. liquor ammonia and then filtered.

Ammonia solution: 20 c.c. liquor ammonia was made up to 100 c.c.

Silver solution: Pure silver nitrate (6.8 g.) was dissolved in 400 c.c. water containing a few drops of concentrated nitric acid. The solution, after filtration, was stored in an amber-coloured bottle. Silver content was estimated by the classical chloride method.

All solutions for the study of interference were generally made by direct weighing.

All reagents used in this investigation were either of Merck's G. R. or Extra pure variety or B.D.H. Analar quality. The EDTA, however, was a B.D.H.-L.R. grade. All p_H adjustments were made with a Cambridge p_H -meter.

Effect of p_H on the Precipitation of Silver.—It was observed that precipitation in slightly acid medium afforded a colloidal, incomplete product, which took a long time (2 hrs.) on the water-bath for coagulation. On the other hand, in ammoniacal medium the precipitates coagulated within 10 to 15 minutes, and good results were obtained.

TABLE I

Silver taken = 0.1080 g.

...	...	5.64	6.14	7.54	8.40	9.06	10.02
Silver found (in g.)	...	0.1053	0.1073	0.1077	0.1075	0.1076	0.1076

Procedure.—To the silver solution (in a volume of 50 c.c.) 10 c. c. of the ammonia solution was added to bring the p_H to the vicinity of 10. The solution was then heated on a water-bath to 60°-70° for about 10 minutes. It was then treated with an excess of a hot 1% reagent solution with constant stirring. Generally, for 100 mg. silver, 20 c.c. of the hot reagent solution was sufficient for complete precipitation. The mixture was then digested on the water-bath for another 10 minutes by which time the precipitate coagulated completely. The precipitate was then filtered through a Gooch crucible (G₃ or G₄) and washed with about 100 c.c. of warm water. The precipitate was finally dried at 120° to a constant weight (about 1½-2 hours) and weighed as AgC₄H₅N₂. Good results were obtained with silver content varying from 10 mg. to 100 mg. For amounts below 5 mg., a micro adaptation of the method is, however, preferable.

TABLE II

Silver taken.	Silver benzimidazole.	Silver found.	Error.
0.1104 g.	0.2318 g.	0.1112 g.	+0.0008 g.
0.0324	0.0676	0.0324	±0
0.0108	0.0224	0.01074	-0.00006
0.0054	0.0112	0.00537	-0.00003

Effect of Ammonium Salts.—It was observed that in presence of an appreciable amount of ammonium salts, precipitation of silver benzimidazole was incomplete; consequently the values were low. So if the silver solution is strongly acidic, neutralisation must be made with dilute NaOH.

TABLE III

Silver taken = 0.1104 g.

Ammonium salt.	Amount added.	Silver benzimidazole.	Silver found.
NH ₄ NO ₃	0.5 g.	0.2315 g.	0.1110 g.
	1.0	0.2288	0.1097
NH ₄ Cl	5.0	0.2183	0.1047
	1.0	0.2117	0.1016

Procedure in presence of Cu, Ni, Co, Mn, Mg, Hg^{II}, Pb, Zn, Cd, Tl, etc.—To the silver solution containing any of these interfering metals was added with stirring 10 c.c. of the ammoniacal EDTA solution and the mixture was then brought to 60°-70° and silver precipitated by excess benzimidazole. Generally, 2 to 3 times the theoretical amount of EDTA, required to complex a particular metal, was used to hold the metal in solution. For metals like iron and chromium, hydroxides of which were slowly acted upon by EDTA, this procedure had to be modified.

Procedure in presence of Iron and Chromium.—To the slightly acid solution of silver and these metals was added 10 c.c. of the simple EDTA (without ammonia), and the mixture was heated at 60°-70° for 5-10 minutes, when the metals were firmly complexed. A little precipitate of Ag-EDTA appeared which, however, dissolved on proper stirring when the solution was made ammoniacal by the addition of 10 c.c. of ammonia solution. Before the addition of the reagent, it was made sure that 20 silver-EDTA precipitate remained undissolved.

Procedure in presence of Al, Be, Ti, UO₂, Th, etc.—Aluminium, beryllium, titanium, etc. were masked by sodium potassium tartrate. To the slightly acidic solution of silver and these metals was added enough (5-10 g.) Rochelle salt (R.S.) and the mixture was afterwards made ammoniacal with 10 c.c. of ammonia solution. If a precipitate of the hydroxide forms, then some more tartrate should be added and the mass nearly boiled to get a clear solution. Afterwards, silver is precipitated as usual with the hot 1% reagent.

TABLE IV

Ions added.	Amount added.	Ag. found.	Ag. taken.	Ions added.	Amount added.	Ag found.	Ag taken.
Cu ²⁺	63.5 mg.	0.1096 g.	0.1104 g.	Mg ²⁺	24.3 mg.	0.1094 g.	0.1104 g.
"	"	0.0539	0.0540	"	"	0.0547	0.0552
Ni ²⁺	58.7	0.1077	0.1080	Mn ²⁺	54.9	0.0536	0.0540
"	"	0.0545	0.0540	Al ³⁺	54	0.1112	0.1104
Pb ²⁺	207.2	0.1074	0.1080	"	"	0.0553	0.0552
"	"	0.0537	0.0540	Be ²⁺	18	0.1110	0.1104
Zn ²⁺	65.3	0.1084	0.1080	"	"	0.0553	0.0552
"	"	0.0539	0.0540	Ti ³⁺	47.9	0.0555	0.0552
Co ²⁺	59.0	0.1094	0.1104	"	"	0.1103	0.1104
"	"	0.1065	0.1080	UO ₂ ²⁺	270	0.1103	0.1104
Cd ²⁺	112.4	0.1070	0.1080	"	"	0.0556	0.0552
"	"	0.0539	0.0540	Th ⁴⁺	232	0.0556	0.0552
Hg ²⁺	200	0.1070	0.1080	"	"	0.1106	0.1104
"	"	0.0536	0.0540	WO ₄ ²⁻	248	0.1108	0.1104
Tl ⁺	204	0.1078	0.1080	"	"	0.0556	0.0552
"	"	0.0542	0.0540	VO ₄ ²⁻	57	0.1106	0.1104
Fe ²⁺	55.8	0.0532	0.0540	"	"	0.0553	0.0552
"	"	0.1070	0.1080	CrO ₄ ²⁻	116	0.1103	0.1104
Cu ⁺	52.1	0.1110	0.1104	"	"	0.0552	0.0552
"	"	0.0552	0.0552	C ₂ O ₄ ²⁻	88	0.1093	0.1104
"	"	"	"	"	"	0.0546	0.0552
"	"	"	"	HPO ₄ ²⁻	95	0.0547	0.0552

Composition of the Precipitate.—The silver benzimidazole precipitate was dried at 120° and then a weighed amount was decomposed by dilute nitric acid ; silver was then determined as chloridé. (Found : Ag, 48.3. $\text{AgC}_7\text{H}_4\text{N}_2$ requires Ag, 47.97 per cent).

Author's grateful thanks are due to Prof. P. Rây and to Dr. P. C. Banerjee for their encouragement and good wishes during the course of this investigation. Thanks are also due to the Ministry of Education, Government of India, for the award of a Senior Research Scholarship which enabled the author to undertake this investigation.

INORGANIC CHEMISTRY LABORATORY,
INDIAN ASSOCIATION FOR THE
CULTIVATION OF SCIENCE,
CALCUTTA-32.

Received October 11, 1955.